

Development of methodics and modeling system of nitrogen and phosphorus load calculation for surface waters of Lithuania
ID Nr.100054

The 1st Interim Report by
UAB „Estonian, Latvian & Lithuanian Environment” and
SIA „Procesu analīzes un izpētes centrs”

Client: Aplinkos Apsaugos Agentūra

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APLINKOS APSAUGOS AGENTŪRA

“AZOTO IR FOSFORO BALANSO IR SUSILAIKYMO SKAIČIAVIMO METODIKŲ BEI PASIŪLYMŲ VANDENS TELKINIŲ APKROVOS TERŠALAIS SKAIČIAVIMO LIETUVOS METODIKAI PARENGIMAS BEI LIETUVOS SITUACIJOS PAGAL PARENGTAS METODIKAS ĮVERTINIMAS“ (PIRKIMO NR. 100054)

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The 1st Interim Report

by

**UAB “Estonian, Latvian & Lithuanian Environment” (ELLE)
and
SIA “Procesu analīzes un izpētes centrs” (PAIC)**

January 2012

Approved by:

Aplinkos apsaugos agentūra		
M _____	M _____	
Date:	Date	
Signature:	Signature:	

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1 Introduction

The project title, translated in to English reflects the overall Project objective and is as follows:

“Assessment of nitrogen and phosphorus budget by means of the development and subsequent application of the surface water quality modelling system (or model) for the physical territory of Lithuania; use of diffuse semi-parametric model(s) to assess the situation in Lithuania using the simulation system developed (or model) and the integration of the developed simulation system (or model) with the other Aplinkos apsaugos agentūros water models”.

The main objective of this project is to meet the requirements of Water Framework Directive and the recommendations of the Helsinki Convention regarding the surface water quality and loads of nutrients into the Baltic Sea.

Lithuanian water quality authorities require efficient and reliable water management, evaluation and forecasting tools to comply with Lithuania's commitments to achieve good water status by 2015 and contribute to the Baltic Sea restoration of good ecological status by 2021. Thus, the modelling systems applied should allow analysis and selection of pollution reduction scenarios associated with changes in land use, agricultural practice, socioeconomic structure, climate change etc. It means that besides an accurate description of hydrological and aquatic chemistry of surface waters, there is a need for decision support systems. Such systems would assess the input information to allow making effective water management decisions.

The concrete aims of the project are:

- Development of a surface water quality modelling system for the territory of Lithuania; the system will be based on parametric process-based mathematical models;
- Assessment of the status of Lithuanian surface waters by the developed modelling system with special emphasis on the elements of phosphorus and nitrogen budget;
- Integration of the developed modelling system with the other water management tools at Lithuanian Environmental protection Agency - Aplinkos apsaugos agentūra (further - AAA).

According to the Technical specification, the following tasks have to be achieved the above aims:

1. Selection of modelling software and development of a water quality modelling system capable of computing at least (1) the distribution and time development of surface water quality components (at least total nitrogen N_{tot} , total phosphorus P_{tot} , nitrate nitrogen NO_3-N , ammonium nitrogen NH_4-N , phosphate phosphorus PO_4-P , biochemical oxygen demand BOD_7 , dissolved oxygen O_2 and particulate sediments, (2) phosphorus and nitrogen loading, retention and transformations;
2. Application of the developed modelling system for calculation of annual and monthly nitrogen and phosphorus loading (from point and diffuse sources), retention and load distribution in river system for the time period 2000-2010 for the territory of Lithuania;

3. Development of the decision support system (DSS) for the identification of critical loads of nitrogen and phosphorus, and nitrate-sensitive areas, and management of scenarios for load reduction. Such DSS will be based on Geographic Information System (GIS);
4. Integration of the developed water quality modelling system with the AAA's river modelling system (based on MIKE 11);
5. Integration of the developed water quality modelling system and AAA's river modelling system (MIKE 11) with the AAA's modelling system of Curonian lagoon and Baltic Sea (based on MIKE 21).

The project has started on May 31 2011. This is the first project report (Interim report), which covers 5 months of the project implementation. The project has made substantial progress during this period. According to the working plan the Interim report is prepared after performing activities A1-A5:

Activity A1. Selection of the appropriate modelling system;
Activity A2. Definition of input data sets and mobilisation of data
Activity A3. Model setup and calibration for the selected pilot basins;
Activity A4. Validation, sensitivity and uncertainty analysis
Activity A5. Model setup and calibration for Lithuania

The respective activities and their results are described in Sections 2.2.1 – 2.2.5 of this interim report.

The Interim report includes description of the organisational setup of project, project progress, and plans for the next reporting.

2 Implementation of the Project

2.1. Organisational setup of the project

The project team consists of employees of Consulting Consortium members UAB “Estonian, Latvian & Lithuanian Environment” (ELLE) and SIA “Procesu analizēs un izpētes centrs” (PAIC).

The project administration and management from the Consortium side is organised by Project Working group (WG), which consists of the Project Manager Uldis Bethers (PAIC), partner’s responsible person for the communication, reporting, data collection Aidas Pivoriūnas (ELLE). Project scientific leader is Agrita Briede (PAIC), but the main modelling expert is Juris Senģikovs (PAIC). The WG had developed the project management scheme, co-ordinating all team work, approve tasks for experts, control and adjust the relevant issues, including the compliance with time schedule, service priorities, reporting, and quality assurance.

The project WG has assigned the concrete tasks to relevant qualified personnel (experts) in the fields of database management, environmental data analysis, modelling, hydrology, aquatic chemistry, engineering, software and information system development.

The participants of the kick-off meeting that has been organised on 9th of May, 2011 in Vilnius, have formed a Project Implementation Group (IG):

AAA appointed its representatives for the technical implementation of the project:

- Rasa Maslauskaitė – Project Manager from AAA, Head of Project Management and Public Procurement Unit;
- Svajūnas Plunge - the leading Technical Coordinator of AAA, Chief Specialist and Watershed Modeller;
- Audrius Šepikas, Chief Specialist;

Project IG has agreed to have a Technical meeting each and every month, starting from June 2011. Project IG has also agreed that all the meetings will have minutes, written by ELLE, later distributed to both Uldis Bethers and Svajūnas Plungē, and the official language of the meeting is English. Decisions made at Technical meeting should be also drawn up and if agreements come they have to be signed. There have been five meetings of the project IG during this project implementation phase, see Annexes for lists of participants and minutes of the meetings.

Finally, the Project IG has agreed that the communication between the members of the WG and AAA should be performed on email basis, project implementation and reporting language is English, except for a Final Report, where the summary should be prepared in Lithuanian.

ELLE has created a special account for project activities and file storage on its ftp server and gave an access to the leading members of IG.

2.2. Activities carried out during the first reporting period

During the first period of the project implementation the Activities 1 to 5 have been developed:

- Activity A1. Selection of the appropriate modelling system;
- Activity A2. Definition of input data sets and mobilisation of data;
- Activity A3. Model setup and calibration for the selected pilot basins;
- Activity A4. Validation, sensitivity and uncertainty analysis;
- Activity A5. Model setup and calibration for Lithuania.

2.2.1. Selection of the appropriate modelling system

The requirements for the modelling system were in details given in the tender technical specification. Making the selection of modelling system we ensured the fulfilment of all requirements (suitability for the purpose, nomenclature of considered parameters, process descriptive spatially and temporally distributed modelling approach, application references of modelling system in other countries, time of system development, availability of source code, scientific coverage of system by publications, integration of modelling system with GIS software, documentation level of the modelling system).

The compliance of proposed modelling system with these requirements has been agreed on the 2nd Progress implementation group meeting on July 4, 2011.

The proposed modelling system is SWAT (Soil and Water Assessment Tool) initially developed by Dr. J.Arnolds of Texas A&M University for USDA Agricultural Research Service. SWAT is an hydrology model with the following capacity of process description and functionality (components): weather data management, surface runoff, return flow, percolation, evapotranspiration, transmission losses, pond and reservoir storage, crop growth and irrigation, groundwater flow, reach routing, nutrient and pesticide loading, water transfer. SWAT can be considered a watershed hydrological transport model.

SWAT is a continuous time model that preferably operates on a daily time step at basin scale. The objective of such a model is to predict the long-term impacts in large basins of management and also timing of agricultural practices within a year (i.e., crop rotations, planting and harvest dates, irrigation, fertilizer application rates and timing). It can be used to simulate at the basin scale water and nutrients cycle. SWAT uses a two-level dissagregation scheme; a preliminary subbasin identification based on topographic criteria, followed by further discretization using land use and soil type considerations. Areas with the same soil type and land use form a Hydrologic Response Unit (HRU), a basic computational unit assumed to be homogeneous in the land cover / soil properties.

SWAT modelling system and its development has been described in numerous scientific papers summarised in Gassman et al (2005) and it has rather comprehensive documentation (e.g. Neitsch et al (2002) for SWAT2005, Neitsch et al (2011) for SWAT2009, Winchell et al (2009) for ArcSWAT). The SWAT resources can be found in WWW at <http://swatmodel.tamu.edu/>.

The usage of the SWAT (and original) model components are illustrated in Figures 1-2. The model components are used to perform three basic tasks.

Figure 1. Scheme of information flow and components of model system during the model setup and calculation phases.

1. **Building of model setup.** SWAT modelling system for Lithuania consists of SWAT setups for particular watersheds. Each such a setup contains multiple files with necessary input information. **ArcSWAT** (Winchell et al (2009)) is a set of SWAT components embedded into ArcMap environment. It uses ArcMap geodatabase which can be processed by MS Access software. ArcSWAT and MS Access are used for the creation of **initial model setup** from the geospatial data (see also Section 2.2.2) and ArcSWAT database (which for the purposes of this project is extended with the records from the Harmonised world soil database, FAO (2009)) via the following steps (Fig.1):
 - a. **ArcSWAT** is used for building model geometry: subdivision of Lithuania into watersheds, subdivision of each watershed into subbasins, assigning reaches to each subbasin and subdivision of the subbasins into hydrological response units..
 - b. **MS Access** is used to fill the geodatabases of each watershed with the relevant geospatial information (see also Section 2.2 for the particular input data and data pre-processing) point source location and respective time series, reservoirs and their parameters, soil data, land use classes, meteorological data, atmospheric deposition, management praxis. Initial model setup is filled with default (process) parameters creating **initial model setup**.
2. **Calculation and visualisation** of the time series for particular catchment (Fig 1).
 - a. Calculation is performed by numerical engine of **SWAT2009** (Neitsch et al (2011)) which produce result files from the ready-to-calculate setups (**Setup 2** in Fig.1).

- b. The visualisation of the results is further performed with or **PAIC SWAT**. The postprocessing functionality of PAIC SWAT is developed for constructing and analysing time graphs, budget calculations and comparison with observations.
3. **Model calibration** is performed by two independent routes (Figs.1-2):
 - a. As **autocalibration** of pre-defined set of parameters as a series of SWAT2009 runs managed by **SWAT CUP** (Abbaspour (2009)) optimisation engine. The result of autocalibration is a modified (calibrated) model **setup 1**.
 - b. As **expert calibration** via analysing of the calculation and manual changing of the model parameters in **PAIC SWAT**. The result of expert calibration is modified (calibrated model **setup 2**).

Figure 2. Scheme of information flow and components of model system during calibration phase.

Thus, the principal components of the model system are (Figs. 1-2):

1. ARCSWAT – used for managing geospatial information and creating initial model setup. ArcMap and MS Access is used for handling the data.
2. SWAT CUP – used for management of the autocalibration and sensitivity analysis.
3. SWAT2009 – used for the calculation of the model results
4. PAIC SWAT – used for (1) hands-on tool for expert calibration, (2) measurement of calibration and validation quantitative results, (3) visualisation of model results.

The advantages of open source software were used to examine the source code; it resulted in re-compilation of SWAT2009 and ArcSWAT software to fulfil the technical requirements of the project. The particular modifications to the source code included:

SWAT2009 modification :

1. File *roures.f* line 277, unmodified transfer of CBOD and DISOX through the reservoir was included. Originally CBOD un DISOX were set to 0 at the outflow.
2. File *hmeas.f* line 80, automatic detection of *relhum* for measured *relhum* data was turned off.
3. *watqual.f* from 2005 version is used.
4. File *operatr.f* (lines 201-224), *readmgt.f* (lines 665-669): the scheduling of tillage operations by heatunits are set as always based on base zero heat units, independent of the plant growth.

Modified ArcSWATdll file allows writing “save” command instead of “saveconc” command to the .fig file.

Working with SWAT one should account the following disagreement between the documentation and the executable files:

1. Wind data should be prepared for 10 m height (not 1,7 m as in documentation)

The original software PAIC SWAT software was developed for the more convenient performing of the data visualisation and modification of the SWAT setups. It is foreseen that the software will be developed throughout the stages of the project; thus, no documentation has been developed at the present stage and this software is not delivered to AAA.

2.2.2. Definition of input data sets and mobilisation of data

Overview

The input data sets for the water quality modelling system are the following:

- Geospatial data;
- Hydrometeorological data series;
- Statistical and/or geospatial data on inhabitants, agricultural parameters for assessment of diffuse pollution sources;
- parameters of point pollution sources.

The WG has asked Nacionalinė žemės tarnyba prie LR žemės ūkio ministerijos to provide the available land databases. For a soil data description the following data has been used: land reclamation state information; soil properties dataset; geospatial background database. Land reclamation state and soaking database contains specified irrigated areas and drained areas, trench or both with different state of reclamation. Soil properties dataset includes soil profile description, physical and agrochemical properties, terrain, land use, parent material, humidity, texture, pH, flooding, land cover, erosion, drainage and anthropogenic impact information. In addition, use of fertilizers in the agriculture, number of cattle, birds, rabbits at the beginning of the year and meteorological data (precipitation, humidity, wind velocity, temperature, solar radiation and dew point) were also included in the dataset.

Geospatial background database includes coordinates, height information and geobjects data (position, area, borders, population, type of settlement, hydrographic objects, coastlines, land cover, roads and road type, railways and railway type, electricity grid, gas and oil lines, heritage objects, towers and buildings).

The WG has also asked AAA to provide the available hydrometeorological and hydrogeological databases. Information about settlements and industrial objects was also supplemented with data on water supply, sewerage and waste water treatment systems, raster dataset of built-up and non-built-up areas. Moreover, position of water extraction points, data on hydropower stations (position, distance to the river mouth, type, power, possibility of risk), type, depth and state of water bodies, information about point source, groundwater pollution and water quality in water bodies (position, dissolved oxygen, yearly and monthly load for N_{tot} , total phosphorus P_{tot} , nitrate nitrogen NO_3-N , ammonium nitrogen NH_4-N , phosphate phosphorus PO_4-P , biochemical oxygen demand BOD_7 , dissolved oxygen O_2 yearly and monthly flow and distance of the point source to the river mouth) were also used.

Pre-processing of input data sets

Let us consider the preprocessing of the initial input information performed during the 1st stage of the project: This description explains the steps done for the preparation of the modelling system.

1. The GIS layers of **catchments** and **rivers** were used for the watershed and subbasin delineation by ArcSWAT (“sub” and “rte” files). The watershed (or SWAT setup) was created in relation with the **hydrometric and/or water quality stations** or logically. Each of 1089 river catchments corresponds to one SWAT subbasin. The map of catchments (SWAT subbasins) for the territory of Lithuania see in Fig.3. The considered river network (with nodes – lower points of each river) see in Fig. 4. The illustration of the watershed and subbasins with hydrometeorological, hydrometric and water quality stations is given in Fig. 5 for the Šušvė watershed.

Fig.3. Catchments (SWAT subbasins) in Lithuania.

Fig. 4. River network (with nodes) in Lithuania.

2. The **DEM of Lithuania** and GIS layers of **point source location and reservoirs** were used altogether with watershed/subbasin location to create the initial setup files (“point”, “res”) by ARCSWAT.

Fig. 5. Šušvė watershed with subbasins. Hydrometeorological (yellow), hydrometric (green) and water quality (red) stations.

- a. Assignment of the pollution time-series to the point sources is described in p.7.
- b. We used the *reservoirs_with_parameters* data file for reservoir parameters. Only the reservoirs that are located on the river network (determined by the spatial join of layer *reservoirs_with_parameters* and layer *Reach* of each of the setups) were used. The spatial intersection of this layer and subbasin geometric shape (layer *Watershed*) was performed to determine the actual subbasin to which the reservoir is attached (and divide the reservoir if it belongs to more than one subbasin) obtaining layer *reservoirs* for each of the setups. The reservoir parameters representing area at the emergency spillway level, volume at the emergency spillway level, area at the principal spillway level, and volume at the principal spillway level (*RES_ESA*, *RES_EVOL*, *RES_PSA*, *RES_PVOL*) were obtained as $RES_ESA = savl1$, $RES_EVOL = vav1/10$, $RES_PSA = snpl1$, $RES_PVOL = vnpl1/10$. The initial volume of water in the reservoir (*RES_VOL*) was set equal to *RES_PVOL*. The reservoir were assumed to operate as „uncontrolled reservoir with the annual release rate” (*IRESCO*=0). Corresponding annual release rate (*RES_RR*) was assumed to be the principal volume of the reservoir divided by 1 year, i.e. $RES_RR = RES_PVOL * 1000 / (365 * 86400)$ [m³/s].
- c. The DEM of Lithuania is shown in Fig. 6, whilst for Šušvė watershed in Fig. 7. The location of point sources is given, respectively, in Figs. 8-9.

3. The **soil data** was processed as follows:

- a. The FAO classification code was assigned to all elements of Lithuanian soil coverage maps 1:10000 (*DirvDB10LT*). The FAO codes were acquired from (1) the respective records of database for unique soil codes, (2) from the well database, (3) for the missing areas (forests) – from the LT soil coverage maps

1:3000000. 41 unique FAO classification codes were found.

Fig. 6. DEM of Lithuania.

Fig. 7. DEM of Šušvė watershed.

Fig. 8. Point source location in Lithuania.

Fig. 9 Point source location in Šušvė watershed.

- b. The records from the HWSD FAO (2009) which correspond to the 41 unique soil code and the samples from Lithuanian territory were retrieved from HWSD by means of manual selection. The correspondence between the FAO codes and HWSD record number is given in Table 1. Each HWSD record contains the soil parameters listed in Table 2; they correspond to either the whole soil layer or 300 mm topsoil or 700 mm subsoil.

Table 1. Established relation between FAO soil codes (SoilName) and record numbers in HWSD (HWSDID).

SoilName	HWSDID								
AB	10400	CMc	10321	GLd	10408	LVg	10357	PZg	10414
ABd	10400	CMd	10321	GLe	10423	LVh	10348	PZh	10409
ABe	10400	CMe	10325	GLk	10419	LVj	10352	RGc	10577
ABg	10400	CMg	10333	GLm	10427	LVk	10341	RGd	8633
ABj	10400	FLc	10438	GLu	9125	PLd	10362	RGe	10454
ARb	10404	FLd	110	HSf	10435	PLe	10367		
ARc	10400	FLe	10441	HSs	10430	PLm	10367		
ARg	10407	FLm	10440	LPk	10357	PLu	10367		
ARh	10400	FLu	10441	LPq	10357	PZf	5108		

Table 2. Soil parameters from HWSD.

HWSD_DATA parameter	Description
DRAINAGE	Drainage class
T_TEXTURE	Texture class
AWC_CLASS	Available water capacity class
T_REF_BULK_DENSITY	Topsoil bulk density, g/cm ³
T_OC	Topsoil organic carbon content, %
T_CLAY	Topsoil clay content, %
T_SILT	Topsoil silt content, %
T_SAND	Topsoil sand content, %
T_GRAVEL	Topsoil gravel content, %
T_ECE	Topsoil electrical conductivity, dS/m
s_REF_BULK_DENSITY	Subsoil bulk density, g/cm ³
s_OC	Subsoil organic carbon content, %
s_CLAY	Subsoil clay content, %
s_SILT	Subsoil silt content, %
s_SAND	Subsoil sand content, %
s_GRAVEL	Subsoil gravel content, %
S_ECE	Subsoil electrical conductivity, dS/m

- c. The soil type related SWAT parameters (*Usersoil* table) were either directly acquired from HWSD, or determined by either SWAT or original methodics. The summary of the methods for the calculation of SWAT soil parameters is given in Table 3. Possible methods are: (1) numeric value, (2) variable from HWSD_DATA, (3) lookup table based on a variable from HWSD_DATA, (4) an equation dependent on HWSD_DATA variables for soil erodibility factor “KUSLE”. For the later method we used “Silt content” for “msilt”, “sand content” for “mvfs”, “clay content” for “mc”, “organic carbon content” for “orgC”, and used lookup Tables 6-7 for obtaining “csoilstr” and “cperm” from “texture class” and “drainage class”, respectively.

Table 3. The variables of ArcSWAT *usersoil* table and method of obtaining them from HWSD.

Usersoil abbreviation	Name	Method
NLAYERS	Number of soil layers	2
HYDGRP	Soil hydrological group	Lookup based on DRAINAGE (Table 4)
SOL_ZMX	Maximum rooting depth of profile, mm	1000
ANION_EXCL	Fraction of porosity from which anions are excluded	0.5
SOL_CRK	Crack volume potential of soil	0.5
SOL_Z1	Depth to bottom of the first soil layer, mm	300
SOL_BD1	Moist bulk density of first soil layer, Mg/m ³	=T_REF_BULK_DENSITY
SOL_AWC1	Available water capacity of first soil layer, mm H ₂ O/mm soil	Lookup based on AWC_CLASS (Table 5)
SOL_K1	Saturated hydraulic conductivity of first soil layer, mm/hr	Lookup based on HYDGRP (Table 4)
SOL_CBN1	Organic carbon content of first soil layer, %	=T_OC
CLAY1	Clay content of first soil layer, %	=T_CLAY
SILT1	Silt content of first soil layer, %	=T_SILT
SAND1	Sand content of first soil layer, %	=T_SAND
ROCK1	Rock content of first soil layer, %	=T_GRAVEL
SOL_ALB1	Moist soil albedo of first soil layer	0.09
USLE_K1	USLE equation soil erodibility factor of first soil layer	Equations 4:1.1.2-4:1.1.4 of SWAT 2005 documentation Neitsch et al (2002)
SOL_EC1	Electrical conductivity of first soil layer	=T_ECE
SOL_Z2	Depth to bottom of the second soil layer, mm	700
SOL_BD2	Moist bulk density of second soil layer, Mg/m ³	=S_REF_BULK_DENSITY
SOL_AWC2	Available water capacity of second soil layer, mm H ₂ O/mm soil	Lookup based on AWC_CLASS (Table 5)
SOL_K2	Saturated hydraulic conductivity of second soil layer, mm/hr	Lookup based on HYDGRP (Table 4)
SOL_CBN2	Organic carbon content of second soil layer, %	=S_OC
CLAY2	Clay content of second soil layer, %	=S_CLAY
SILT2	Silt content of second soil layer, %	=S_SILT
SAND2	Sand content of second soil layer, %	=S_SAND
ROCK2	Rock content of second soil layer, %	=S_GRAVEL
SOL_ALB2	Moist soil albedo of second soil layer	0.09
USLE_K2	USLE equation soil erodibility factor of second soil layer	Equations 4:1.1.2-4:1.1.4 of SWAT 2005 documentation Neitsch et al (2002)
SOL_EC2	Electrical conductivity of second soil layer	=S_ECE

Table 4. Lookup table relating drainage class and soil hydrological group.

HWSD drainage class	HWSD drainage class name	Soil hydrological group	Saturated hydraulic conductivity, mm/hr
1	Very Poor	D	50
2	Poor	C	20
3	Imperfectly	C	20
4	Moderately Well	B	5
5	Well	B	5
6	Somewhat Excessive	A	2
7	Excessive	A	2

Table 5. Lookup table relating AWC class and SOL_AWC values:

AWC_CLASS	SOL_AWC
1	0.15
2	0.125
3	0.1
4	0.075
5	0.05
6	0.015
7	0

Table 6. Lookup table relating HWSD texture class with *csoilstr* used in equation for calculating of *USLE_K*.

HWSD texture class	HWSD texture class name	<i>csoilstr</i>	<i>csoilstr</i> name, SWAT 2005 documentation Neitsch et al (2002), p.228
1	Coarse	3	Medium or coarse granular
2	Medium	2	Fine granular
3	Fine	1	Very fine granular

Table 7. Lookup table relating HWSD drainage class with *cperm* used in equation for calculating of *USLE_K*

:HWSD drainage class	HWSD drainage class name	Cperm	cperm name, SWAT 2005 documentation Neitsch et al (2002), p.228
1	Very Poor	6	Very slow
2	Poor	5	Slow
3	Imperfectly	4	Slow to moderate
4	Moderately Well	3	Moderate
5	Well	2	Moderate to rapid
6	Somewhat Excessive	1	Rapid
7	Excessive	1	Rapid

- d. The SWAT database was updated by these selected HWSD records.
- e. The shape and grid files covering the whole territory of Lithuania were created. The example of the soil grid for the whole Lithuania and the Šušvė watershed is shown in, respectively, Figs. 10-11.

Fig. 10. Soil type distribution in Lithuania.

Fig. 11. Soil type distribution in Šušvė watershed.

4. The declared **land use** was available for the agricultural land of Lithuania. The Corine land cover database was used for the rest of the territory. The following steps were performed to assign 41 unique ArcSWAT land use identifier (corresponding to particular crop) to particular land use polygon of initial data; additionally all land uses were divided (generalised into 5 groups (agricultural, pastures, forests, urban and water) for applying different SWAT management praxis algorithms:
 - a. The declared crops were translated to English and assigned to agricultural ArcSWAT land use classes. The declared territories included also pastures and apple-gardens (see Table 8).
 - b. The ArcSWAT land use for the rest of the territory was assigned according to CORINE classification, see corresponding codes in Table 2. WETF and WETN land use types were applied for the calculation of the wetland fraction of each subbasin.
 - c. The shape and grid files of the land use was prepared by ArcMap. See the example of the land use grid for the Šušvė watershed in Fig. 12.
5. Unique combinations of the soil type (p.3), and the land use (p.4) are a basis for distinguishing **hydrological response units** (HRU) within each subbasin. “hru” file were generated by ArcSWAT.

Table 8. ARCSWAT land use (crop) classes, source of classification and corresponding CORINE codes.

ARCSWAT land use code	Land use type	Source of classification	Corine code
AGRR, ALFA, BARL, CANP, CORN, CRRT, EGGP, FESC, FLAX, FPEA, GRBN, LENT, OATS, PEAS, POTA, RYE, SCRN, SGBT, SOYB, STRW, SWHT, TIMO,TOMA,WWHT	Agricultural	Declared land use	N/A
ORCD	Agricultural	CORINE, declared land use	222
AGRC	Agricultural	CORINE, declared land use	211, 242
BROM, CLVR	Pastures	Declared land use	N/A
RYEG	Pastures	CORINE	321, 322
WPAS	Pastures	CORINE	231
APPL	Forest	Declared land use	N/A
FRSD	Forest	CORINE	324, 333
FRSE	Forest	CORINE	312
FRST	Forest	CORINE	311, 313
WETF	Forest	CORINE	411, 412
UIDU	Urban	CORINE	121, 122, 123, 124
URHD	Urban	CORINE	111
URLD	Urban	CORINE	131, 132, 133, 141, 142
URML	Urban	CORINE	112
WATR	Water	CORINE	511, 512, 521
WETN	Water	CORINE	331

6. SWAT requires daily **meteorological data series** (precipitation, air temperature – minimum and maximum values, wind velocity, humidity and solar radiation) as well as data for **atmospheric deposition of nitrogen**.

- a. The hourly meteorological data were used for determining daily temperature extremes. The meteorological data were assigned to every of the subbasins (Figs. 3 and 13) of Lithuania from the closest of the meteorological station (Fig.13 for the location of the meteorological stations where the time series of observation data were supplied). The daily values of the meteorological dataset was used to produce meteorological data files (“wgn”, “pcp”, “tmp”, “hmd” and “slr”). The weather generator file “wgn” is only formally needed for running the SWAT model; weather generator was not used due to the availability of continuous observation data for the time period used further in the calculations.

Fig. 12. Land use distribution in Šušvė watershed.

Fig. 13. Meteorological stations, precipitation stations, and mean annual precipitation assigned for each of the subbasins.

Table 9. Crop identifier and particular plant parameters for different land use types.

Land use code	CROPID	Land use class	PHU	PLANTHU	HarvestHU	FERTHU
AGRC	3	Agricultural	1507	0.03	1.1	0.2
AGRR	2	Agricultural	966	0.21	1.2	0.21
ALFA	52	Agricultural	1057	0.12	1	0.2
APPL	93	Forest				
BARL	31	Agricultural	1422	0.12	1.1	0.2
BROM	37	Pasture				
CANP	75	Agricultural	1328	0.12	1.1	0.2
CLVR	54	Pasture				
CORN	19	Agricultural	966	0.21	1.2	0.21
CRRT	72	Agricultural	1086	0.15	1.1	0.2
EGGP	86	Agricultural	634	0.3	1	0.3
FESC	38	Agricultural	1106	0.12	1	0.2
FLAX	65	Agricultural	1228	0.12	1.2	0.12
FPEA	62	Agricultural	1178	0.12	1.2	0.2
FRSD	7	Forest				
FRSE	8	Forest				
FRST	6	Forest				
GRBN	84	Agricultural	596	0.3	1.2	0.3
LENT	60	Agricultural	1041	0.12	1.2	0.2
OATS	32	Agricultural	1331	0.12	1.1	0.2
ORCD	4	Agricultural	1086	0.15	1	0.2
PEAS	63	Agricultural	870	0.12	1.2	0.2
POTA	70	Agricultural	938	0.15	1.1	0.2
RYE	30	Agricultural	1014	0.12	1.1	0.2
RYEG	44	Pasture				
SCRN	21	Agricultural	348	0.42	1.2	0.42
SGBT	69	Agricultural	1185	0.12	1.1	0.2
SOYB	56	Agricultural	653	0.3	1.2	0.3
STRW	91	Agricultural	609	0.3	1	0.3
SWHT	27	Agricultural	1507	0.12	1.1	0.2
TIMO	35	Agricultural	803	0.21	1	0.21
TOMA	92	Agricultural	634	0.3	1	0.3
UIDU		Urban				
URHD		Urban				
URLD		Urban				
URML		Urban				
WATR	18	Water				
WETF	10	Forest				
WETN	11	Water				
WPAS	14	Pasture				

Land use code	CROPID	Land use class	PHU	PLANTHU	HarvestHU	FERTHU
WWHT	28	Agricultural	1507	0.03	1.1	0.2

- c. For the **agricultural** land the management praxis contained 6 steps for each agricultural land use – spring plow, planting, fertilizer application, continuous fertilisation, kill and harvest operation, and fall plow. The praxis was applied as follows
:
- i. General **spring plow** operation (*tillID=2* from *till.dat*), was scheduled at fraction of base zero heat units equal to 0.02. Sping plow was not implemented for landuse codes AGRC and WWHT (*cropid* 3 and 28)

Table 10. List of considered plants and their parameters.

Abbreviation	Full name	Optimal temperature	Base temperature	Drying HU	Days to reach maturity
AGRC	Agricultural Land-Close-grown	18	0	0.1	110
AGRR	Agricultural Land-Row Crops	25	8	0.2	120
ALFA	Alfalfa	20	4	0	90
BARL	Spring Barley	25	0	0.1	105
CANP	Spring Canola-Polish	21	5	0.1	120
CORN	Corn	25	8	0.2	120
CRRT	Carrot	24	7	0.1	120
EGGP	Eggplant	26	15	0	100
FESC	Tall Fescue	15	0	0	90
FLAX	Flax	22.5	5	0.2	110
FPEA	Field Peas	15	1	0.2	100
GRBN	Green Beans	19	10	0.2	85
LENT	Lentils	20	3	0.2	85
OATS	Oats	15	0	0.1	105
ORCD	Orchard	20	7	0	120
PEAS	Garden or Canning Peas	14	5	0.2	100
POTA	Potato	22	7	0.1	100
RYE	Rye	12.5	0	0.1	90
SCRN	Sweet Corn	24	12	0.2	120
SGBT	Sugarbeet	18	4	0.1	100
SOYB	Soybean	25	10	0.2	120
STRW	Strawberry	32	10	0	90
SWHT	Spring Wheat	18	0	0.1	110
TIMO	Timothy	25	8	0	90
TOMA	Tomato	22	10	0	100
WWHT	Winter Wheat	18	0	0.1	110

- ii. **Planting** operation was scheduled at a fraction of base zero heat units dependent on the crop (see table 9, column *PLANTHU*). The numbers of potential heat units to bring plants to maturity are also included in Table 9, column *PHU*. *PLANTHU* and *PHU* were calculated by

Potential Heat Unit Program
<http://swatmodel.tamu.edu/software/potential-heat-unit-program/>.

Required input data items for this program are (1) the weather long-term maximum and minimum temperature data, (2) the base or minimum temperature required for the plant growth, (3) the average number of days for the plant to reach maturity. The long term temperature data was taken from the Dotnuva meteorological station. Base temperatures and number of days to reach maturity for the considered plants are summarized in Table 10.

- iii. **Fertilizer application.** Fertilizers were applied as two separate applications – one for mineral nitrogen and another for phosphorus, scheduled at fraction of plant heat units *FERTHU*, see Table 9. The scheduling of fertilizer application were selected as $FERTHU = \max(0, 2; PLANTHU)$. The amount of applied nitrogen and phosphorus was calculated from the fertilizer database (fert id 1 and 2, respectively). The geometric shapes of HRUs within each setup (layer *FullHRU*) were geometrically intersected with the administrative division of supplied agricultural statistics data (layer *counties2004.shp*, data by counties) obtaining layer *FullHRU_counties2004* in the ArcMap project of each of the setups. The fields *MINN_HA* and *MINP_HA*, representing mineral nitrogen and mineral phosphorus application per hectare of agricultural land were used to calculate the corresponding amount of applied fertilizer (*FRT_KG*) in each of the HRUs. It should be noted that one HRU can be located in multiple counties, therefore area weighted average for each of the counties that are present in the particular HRU were calculated.
 - iv. **Continuous fertilization** represents application of manure. The field *SGV_TANKIS* from the agricultural statistics data, representing density of standard animals per hectare of agricultural land was used, assuming that each of the standard animals is annually producing 100 kg of nitrogen and 17 kg of phosphorus. Special fertilizer type (*fertID=55, fertname=SGV*) was introduced for this application to specify the amounts of organic and inorganic fertilizers. Each unit of this fertilizer contains (1) 0.25 units of mineral nitrogen 99% of which is ammonia; (2) 0.07 units of mineral phosphorus; (3) 0.75 units of organic nitrogen; (4) 0.1 unit of organic phosphorus. The same geospatial intersection layer as in p.(iii) was used. The continuous fertilization was scheduled to start at a fraction of potential plant heat units 0.15 and last for *FERT_DAYS=190* days. Application frequency (*IFRT_FREQ*) was set to 1 day. Thus, the amount of fertilizer applied in each application is $CFRT_KG = SGV_TANKIS * 100 / FERT_DAYS$
 - v. **Harvest and kill** operation was scheduled at a fraction of plant heat units between 1.0 and 1.2 (see table 9). Depending on a crop type it accounts for the necessary additional crop drying time (see table 10).
 - vi. General **fall plow** operation (*tillID=1* from *till.dat*) was scheduled at fraction of base zero heat units equal to 0.9. It should be noted here that original source code of SWAT2009 was modified to allow for only base zero scheduling of tillage operations.
- d. For the **pastures** the continuous fertilization and grazing was applied. The permanent (without planting and harvesting) grass cover of pastures was

assumed with initial biomass 5000 kg/ha and the number of heat units to bring plant to maturity 3000 (i.e. to avoid bringing grass to maturity during one vegetation season). The continuous fertilizing was applied identically to continuous fertilization of the agricultural land (p.8-c-iv). The grazing of the grass by standard animals was assumed simultaneously with continuous fertilisation for 190 days long period starting at $f=0,15$.

- e. Management “mgt” files of SWAT setups were prepared by ArcSWAT.

2.2.3. Model setup, calibration and validation for the selected pilot basins

Overview

Within this activity two pilot basins (Graisupis and Šušve) and time periods have been agreed with AAA, and model setup, calibration and validation have been performed for the chosen catchments and time periods.

The calibration will be performed for water discharge, N_{tot}, total phosphorus P_{tot}, nitrate nitrogen NO₃-N, ammonium nitrogen NH₄-N, phosphate phosphorus PO₄-P, biochemical oxygen demand BOD₇, dissolved oxygen O₂ and sediment concentrations.

Model setups

The catchment of Graisupis river comprises 14.2 km². It was intended for showing ability of SWAT for detailed spatial and time resolution. The basic setup of Graisupis contains 9 subbasins and 39 HRU. Additional simple setup (1 subbasin, 2 HRU) was created for parameter studies. The delineation of the Graisupis subbasins is shown in Fig 14, soil types in Fig 15 and land use in Fig 16.

Fig. 14. Catchment of Graisupis river: subbasin delineation, reaches, meteorological and hydrometric/water quality stations.

The area of Šušve catchment is 1180 km². It was Intended for illustrating performance of SWAT with typical project spatial and time resolution. The basic setup of Šušve contains 13 subbasins and 1054 HRU. The delineation of the Sušve subbasins is shown in Fig 5, soil types in Fig. 11 and land use in Fig. 12. The model setups for both watershed were built

according to the methodics described in Sections 2.2.1-2.2.2.

Fig. 15. Soil type distribution in Graispis watershed.

Fig. 16. Land use distribution in Graispis watershed.

Calibration and validation – Šušve

The calibration for the hydraulic (Q) and water quality (WQ) parameters in Šušve was performed for, respectively, Years 2003-2007 and 2000-2005. This shift in time occurred due to the discharge data is available since 2003. The rest of observation period (2008-2010 for Q, and 2006-2010 for WQ) was considered as validation period. The number of required water quality parameters does not allowed for autocalibration, and the achieved calibration results (see Table 10) are acquired by mainly expert calibration.

We include the full table of calibration parameters due to Šušve basin was intended as the pilot basin for the development of calibration methodics for the whole Lithuania. The Table contains the full set of the SWAT parameters which were deviated from the default values stating the reason of inclusion of the particular parameter into the table.

Table 10. Calibration results for the Šušve watershed.

Abbreviation	SWAT file(s)	Name	Units	value	Reason / Decision
CDN	BSN	Denitrification exponential rate coefficient		0,0603	NO3 calibration
CMN	BSN	Rate factor for humus mineralization of active organic nitrogen		0,001	NO3 calibration
NPERCO	BSN	Nitrogen percolation coefficient		0,134	NO3 calibration
RCN	BSN	Concentration of nitrogen in rainfall	mg N/kg	0,72	Set from atmospheric deposition data
RSDCO	BSN	Residue decomposition coefficient		0,035	NO3, PO4 calibration
SDNCO	BSN	Denitrification threshold water content		0,019	NO3 calibration
SFTMP	BSN	Snowfall temperature	°C	0,5	Q calibration
SMFMN	BSN	Melt factor for snow on December 21	mm H2O/°C-day	4,5	Q calibration
SMTMP	BSN	Snow melt base temperature	°C	0,8	Q calibration
SPCON	BSN	Linear parameter for calculating the maximum amount of sediment that can be reentrained during channel sediment routing		0,0001	Sediment calibration
SURLAG	BSN	Surface runoff lag time	day-1	0,32	Q calibration
ALPHA_BF	GW	Baseflow alpha factor	day-1	0,07	Q calibration
GW_DELAY	GW	Groundwater delay	day	0,3	Q calibration
GW_REVP	GW	Groundwater revap coefficient		0,02	Q calibration
GWQMN	GW	Threshold depth of water in the shallow aquifer required for return flow to occur	mm	100	set equal to SHALLST

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HLIFE_N GW	GW	Half-life of nitrate in the shallow aquifer	days	1000	NO3 calibration
REVAPM N	GW	Threshold depth of water in the shallow aquifer for revap to occur	mm	125	Q calibration
SHALLST	GW	Initial depth of water in the shallow aquifer	mm	100	Set to fixed value>>0
CANMX	HRU	Maximum canopy storage	mm	10	Q calibration
ESCO	HRU	Soil evaporation compensation factor		0,01	Q calibration
OV_N	HRU	Manning's n value for overland flow		0,14	Q calibration
CN2	MGT	Initial SCS CN II value		-15%	Q, sediment, N-org, P-org calibration
CH_COV	RTE	Channel cover factor		1	Sediment calibration
CH_EROD	RTE	Channel erodibility factor		0	Sediment calibration
CH_K2	RTE	Effective hydraulic conductivity of main channel bed	mm/hr	0	Fixed value, because we have perennial streams
CH_N2	RTE	Manning's n value for main channel		0,06	Q calibration
SOL_AWC(1,2)	SOL	Available water capacity		30%	Q calibration
SOL_K(1,2)	SOL	Saturated hydraulic conductivity	mm/hr	500%	Q calibration
USLE_K(1,2)	SOL	USLE equation soil erodibility factor		-50%	Sediment calibration
BC1	SWQ	Rate constant for biological oxidation of NH4 to NO2 in the reach at 20° C	day-1	4	NH4 calibration
BC2	SWQ	Rate constant for biological oxidation of NO2 to NO3 in the reach at 20° C	day-1	5	Set to maximum, because NO2 is not modelled
BC3	SWQ	Rate constant for hydrolysis of organic N to NH4 in the reach at 20° C	day-1	0,1	N-org, NH4 calibration
BC4	SWQ	Rate constant for mineralization of organic P to dissolved P in the reach at 20° C	day-1	0,45	P-org, PO4 calibration
RK1	SWQ	Carbonaceous biological oxygen demand deoxygenation rate coefficient in the reach at 20° C	day-1	0,03	BOD7 calibration
RK2	SWQ	Oxygen reaeration rate in accordance with Fickian diffusion in the reach at 20° C	day-1	1	Dissolved oxygen calibration
RK3	SWQ	Rate of loss of carbonaceous biological oxygen demand due to settling in the reach at 20° C	day-1	0,01	BOD7 calibration
RS1	SWQ	Local algal settling rate in the reach at 20°C	m/day	0,4	N-org, P-org and N-total/P-total calibration

RS2	SWQ	Benthic (sediment) source rate for dissolved phosphorus in the reach at 20°C	mg dissolved P/(m ² ·day)	0,001	Set to minimum
RS3	SWQ	Benthic source rate for NH ₄ -N in the reach at 20°C	mg NH ₄ -N/(m ² ·day)	0,0001	Set to minimum
RS4	SWQ	Rate coefficient for organic N settling in the reach at 20°C	day ⁻¹	0,07	N-org and N-total calibration
RS5	SWQ	Organic phosphorus settling rate in the reach at 20°C	day ⁻¹	0,55	P-org and P-total calibration

The measure of calibration (and validation) success was agreed with AAA as a compliance with guidelines of Moriasi et al (2007). In essence the above paper use Nash-Sutcliffe efficiency NSE and the deviation from the long term mass bias PBIAS as a measure of calibration success.

Table 11. Calibration and validation efficiency for Šušve and Graisupis catchments.

Watershed		Šušve	Šušve	Graisupis	Graisupis
Aim		Calibration	Validation	Calibration	Validation
Time period, Q		2003-2007	2008-2010	2000-2004	2005-2008
Time period, WQ		2000-2005	2006-2010	2000-2004	2005-2009
Qdaily	NSE	0,58	0,73	0,63	0,50
Qmonthly	NSE	0,72	0,87	0,81	0,65
N-NO ₃	NSE	0,6	0,53	0,70	0,32
Q	PBIAS	-9,4%	9,8%	-6,20%	3,10%
N-NO ₃	PBIAS	-16,00%	17,20%	-8,10%	11,20%
N-NH ₄	PBIAS	6,80%	-9,80%	23,40%	-63,20%
N-Org	PBIAS	-3,40%	-22,20%	19,70%	-64,80%
P-PO ₄	PBIAS	-23,20%	17,60%	23,20%	175,40%
P-Org	PBIAS	33,30%	-3,10%	63,90%	-92,70%
SS	PBIAS	-0,20%	14,40%	No data	No data
BOD ₇	PBIAS	7,30%	-33,30%	20,90%	-31,90%
DOX	PBIAS	-4,80%	26,20%	-8,10%	5,60%

 very good satisfactory
 good unsatisfactory

The summary of the calibration results are given in Table 11, while the time graphs of the observed and calculated daily and monthly discharges, monthly loads of N-NO₃, N-NH₄, N-org, P-PO₄, P-Org, suspended sediments, BOD₇ and dissolved oxygen are presented in Figs 17-26. The time graphs contain all calculation periods, whilst the calibration and validation periods are separated in Table and color –coded according to Moriasi et al (2007).

Fig. 17. Nevezis - Šušve. Daily discharge. Green – model, red – observations.

Fig. 18. Nevezis - Šušve. Monthly discharge. Green – model, red – observations

Fig. 19. Nevezis - Šušve. Monthly NO₃ load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 20. Nevezis - Šušve. Monthly NH₄ load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 21. Nevezis - Šušve. Monthly N-Org load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 22. Nevezis - Šušve. Monthly P-PO4 load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 23. Nevezis - Šušve. Monthly P-Org load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 24. Nevezis - Šušve. Monthly suspended sediment load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 25. Nevezis - Šušve. Monthly BOD7 load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 26. Nevezis - Šušve. Monthly DO load, green – model, red dots – observations.

The calibration and validation results may be estimated as good to very good for discharge according to NSE criteria. NSE criterion is significantly lower for all WQ parameters. Regarding the mean mass flow (PBIAS criteria) the calibration results are good to very good for all considered parameters for both calibration and validation periods.

Calibration and validation – Graisupis

The calibration of the hydrological and water quality model of Graisupis catchment is performed for time period 2000-2004, and the validation – for time period 2005-2008 (2005-2009 for WQ parameters). The summary of the calibration results are given in Table 11, while the time graphs of the observed and calculated daily and monthly discharges, monthly loads of N-NO₃, N-NH₄, N-org, P-PO₄, P-Org, BOD₇ and dissolved oxygen are presented in Figs 27-35. The time graphs contain all calculation periods, whilst the calibration and validation periods are separated in Table 11.

The calibration results are very good (according to Moriasi et al (2007)) with respect the NSE for water discharges and nitrate fluxes, and PBIAS for all parameters with exception of satisfactory results for P-org. For the validation period only satisfactory results are achieved for N-NH₄ and N-org and even unsatisfactory results – for phosphorus. We assume that this is related to the changes of the application of fertilisers in the Graisupis catchment – the small catchment may suffer a greater influence from the interannual and spatial deviations from the statistically-determined amount of applied fertilisers.

Table 12. Calibration results – model parameters of Graisupis basin (listed parameters which differ from the Šušve model parameters).

Abbreviation	SWAT file(s)	Name	Units	Value
CN2	MGT	Initial SCS CN II value		-0,5%
BC1	SWQ	Rate constant for biological oxidation of NH ₄ to NO ₂ in the reach at 20° C	day-1	2
BC3	SWQ	Rate constant for hydrolysis of organic N to NH ₄ in the reach at 20° C	day-1	0,25
BC4	SWQ	Rate constant for mineralization of organic P to dissolved P in the reach at 20° C	day-1	1,5
RK3	SWQ	Rate of loss of carbonaceous biological oxygen demand due to settling in the reach at 20° C	day-1	0,16
RS1	SWQ	Local algal settling rate in the reach at 20°C	m/day	1,1
RS4	SWQ	Rate coefficient for organic N settling in the reach at 20°C	day-1	0,65
RS5	SWQ	Organic phosphorus settling rate in the reach at 20°C	day-1	1,80

The values of model parameters which differ from the Šušve basin model parameters are summarized in Table 12. One have to consider that the difference in the calibration parameters values for smaller (Graisupis) and larger (Šušve) basins is mainly related to the stram parameters, i.e. to the parameterization of the water quality processes in the river.

Fig. 27. Graisupis. Daily discharge. Green – model, red – observations.

Fig. 28. Graisupis. Monthly discharge. Green – model, red – observations

Fig. 29. Graisupis. Monthly NO₃ load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 30. Graisupis. Monthly NH₄ load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 31. Graisupis. Monthly N-Org load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 32. Graisupis. Monthly P-PO4 load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 33. Graisupis. Monthly P-Org load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 34. Graisupis. Monthly BOD7 load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 35. Graisupis. Monthly DO load, green – model, red dots – observations

2.2.4. Sensitivity and uncertainty analysis

Uncertainty analysis

The uncertainty of the modelling of water quality related to three major factors: (1) objective uncertainty of the input data, (2) objective uncertainty of the observation data used for model forcing and calibration, (3) subjective uncertainty of the model assumptions including the calibration solutions and the model process description itself. The modeller should cope with all three sorts of uncertainties in a manner to decrease their possible adverse effects. The practical solution for the dealing with mentioned three types of uncertainty are:

Table 13. Summary of uncertainty issues for water quality modelling in Lithuania.

Uncertainty	Level	Comments / actions
Geospatial information: watershed, rivers, terrain	Low to negligible	None
Soil data	Medium	Model is sensitive to soil data; uncertainty must be treated via calibration
Land use	Medium to low	The land use is rather well defined. However for longer calculation periods it may change.
Point sources	High	Point sources change in time and may be unaccounted / incorrectly reported. Adopted solution – assumption of highest possible loads.
Cattle	High	Statistics are not related to subbasins. Solution – robust assumptions.
Fertilisers and their application	High	Statistics are not related to subbasins. Solution – robust assumptions.
Hydrometeorological input data	Medium to low	Hydrometeorological data are qualitative but may not represent particular subbasins. Solution – allow calibration of precipitation.
Observations of modelled parameters (calibration basis)	Medium	Monthly values of WQ observations may not represent the monthly average values. Solution calibration to reduce PBIAS
Selection of the modelling system	Low	None

1. Reduction of the uncertainty interval, and if not possible – trying to develop robust methods for assuming uncertain input data.
2. Correcting systematic errors and/or screening out outlying data.
3. Avoiding non-physical modes of the solution of the model system.

The evaluation of uncertainty sources for the water quality model in this project is summarised in Table 13.

The quantitative estimation of uncertainty is performed via SUFI-2 method provided with the autocalibration functionality of SWAT CUP2, Abbaspour (2009). The method estimates p-factor – the amount (percentage) of the measured data captured by the 95% of the model runs performed during the autocalibration procedure. Author claims that such an evaluation

method accounts for all possible uncertainty sources and may be used for quantifying an uncertainty of the final (optimum) autocalibration parameter set. Another measure of uncertainty in SUFI-2 is the R-factor – an average thickness of the 95% prediction uncertainty divided by the standard deviation of the measured data. For the detailed application of the method with SWAT simulations, see, for instance Schol et al (2008).

The ranges of P-factor is between 0 and 100%, whilst of R-factor – between 0 and infinity. We applied the method for the autocalibration of discharge time series of Graisupis and Šušve, The results of uncertainty measure is summarised in Table 14.

Table 14. Quantitative values of uncertainties for Graisupis and Šušve model setups.

Catchment	P-factor	R-factor
Graisupis	77%	0,73
Šušve	55%	1,34
Acceptable values	> 50%	< 2

One may consider that for the smaller Graisupis basin the model uncertainty is lower; it is still acceptable for Šušve. .

Sensitivity analysis

The sensitivity analysis was performed as a part of parameter studies to select the parameters for the calibration. The SWAT CUP autocalibration functionality measures the sensitivity of the particular parameters. We used the calibration periods of Graisupis and Šušve setups for the sensitivity analysis according to Abbaspour (2009). The method implies using t-test (linear regression analysis of the set of autocalibration runs) and provides two sensitivity outputs for each of considered model parameters: (1) t-stat as a measure of sensitivity (larger values means more sensitive) and (2) p-values as a significance of the sensitivity (values closer to zero are more significant).

The results of sensitivity analysis are presented in Tables 15 and 16, for, respectively, Graisupis and Šušve basins. The parameters were selected to represent soil hydraulic properties, groundwater and surface water flow, and snow processes and drainage – see color code in Tables.

One may consider that the sensitivity of the particular parameter depends on the selected set of the parameters. In the same time it is evident that at least one parameter from each of parameter groups (at least groundwater, surface water and snow) has high sensitivity to model performance in each autocalibration step.

One may conclude that different parameters are sensitive for small and large calculation domains; it may be explained by the reason that run-off network is not detailed for larger domains and the model turns from „more physical” into „more conceptual”. In the same time the most sensitive parameters are found for both basins in the same parameter groups, responsible for calibrating surface runoff, baseflow and water storage.

Table 15. Parameter sensitivity study for Graisupis setup.

Parameter Name	Min_value	Max_value	Fitted_Value	t-Stat	P-Value
r__CN2.MGT	-0,3	0,5	-0,24	-34,32	0,00
v__OV_N.HRU	0,04	0,3	0,14	29,37	0,00
v__GW_DELAY.GW	0,1	31	0,32	-22,53	0,00
v__SURLAG.BSN	0,1	2	0,75	-21,09	0,00
v__ALPHA_BF.GW	0,01	0,15	0,13	19,40	0,00
v__SMFMN.BSN	2,5	6	4,34	-9,92	0,00
v__SMTMP.BSN	0,4	1,5	0,75	7,28	0,00
v__CANMX.HRU	0,5	30	23,25	7,06	0,00
r__SOL_AWC(1,2).SOL	-0,5	1	0,77	4,77	0,00
v__GW_REVAP.GW	0,01	0,1	0,07	-1,85	0,06
v__CH_N2.RTE	0,04	0,12	0,05	1,73	0,08
v__SFTMP.BSN	0,1	1,5	1,32	1,60	0,11
v__REVAPMN.GW	200	1000	803,80	-1,58	0,12
v__ESCO.HRU	0,001	0,95	0,83	-1,07	0,28
r__SOL_K(1,2).SOL	-0,5	1	0,58	-0,09	0,93

soil parameters

groundwater param.

surface water

snow parameters

Table 16. Parameter sensitivity study for Šušve setup.

Parameter Name	Min_value	Max_value	Fitted_Value	t-Stat	P-Value
r__CN2.MGT	-0,3	0,5	-0,27	-84,20	0,00
v__CH_N2.RTE	0,04	0,12	0,07	33,61	0,00
r__SOL_AWC(1,2).SOL	-0,5	1	0,74	18,68	0,00
v__OV_N.HRU	0,04	0,3	0,25	17,16	0,00
v__SURLAG.BSN	0,1	2	1,93	-12,38	0,00
v__GW_DELAY.GW	0,1	31	2,32	-9,43	0,00
v__SMFMN.BSN	2,5	6	2,66	-8,30	0,00
v__ESCO.HRU	0,001	0,95	0,69	-7,09	0,00
v__ALPHA_BF.GW	0,01	0,15	0,10	6,90	0,00
v__CANMX.HRU	0,5	30	1,78	4,95	0,00
v__SMTMP.BSN	0,4	1,5	1,41	-3,47	0,00
v__SFTMP.BSN	0,1	1,5	0,92	-2,41	0,02
r__SOL_K(1,2).SOL	-0,5	1	0,39	0,78	0,43
v__REVAPMN.GW	200	1000	543,00	-0,40	0,69
v__GW_REVAP.GW	0,01	0,1	0,01	-0,27	0,79

soil parameters

groundwater param.

surface water

snow parameters

2.2.5. Model setup and calibration for Lithuania

The developed model setup methods (section 2.2.2) allow for the preparation of the SWAT model setups for any watershed of Lithuania for the further calculation of N and P loads and fluxes for time period 2000-2010 in the 2nd stage of the project.

The methodics was applied for the upstream watersheds; for the downstream watersheds we defined the upstream watershed which inflows into upper point of the reach. All setups supplied electronically are summarised in Table 17.

Table 17. The list of watershed setups for the territory of Lithuania.

Subbasin	Setup_Name	Subbasin	Watershed	Directory
Bartuva	Apse	Bartuva	Apšė	Bartuva/Apse
Bartuva	Bartuva_Skuodas	Bartuva	Bartuva	Bartuva/Bartuva_Skuodas
Dauguva	497	Dauguva		Dauguva/497
Dauguva	514	Dauguva		Dauguva/514
Dauguva	Bivyte	Dauguva	Birvėta	Dauguva/Bivyte
Dauguva	Druksa	Dauguva	Drūkša	Dauguva/Druksa
Dauguva	Dysna	Dauguva	Dysna	Dauguva/Dysna
Dauguva	Ilukste	Dauguva	Lukšta	Dauguva/Ilukste
Dauguva	Laukesa	Dauguva	Laukesa	Dauguva/Laukesa
Dauguva	Rauda	Dauguva	Rauda	Dauguva/Rauda
Dauguva	Raukuta	Dauguva	Raukuta	Dauguva/Raukuta
Dubysa	Dubysa	Dubysa	Dubysa	Dubysa/Dubysa
Jura	Ezeruona	Jūra	Ežeruona	Jura/Ezeruona
Jura	Jura_Gals	Jūra	Jūra	Jura/Jura_Gals
Jura	Jura_Taurage	Jūra	Jūra	Jura/Jura_Taurage
Jura	Sesupe_Skirgalai	Jūra	Skirgailai	Jura/Sesupe_Skirgalai
Lielupe_Sudupes	194	Lielupes mažieji intakai		Lielupe_Sudupes/194
Lielupe_Sudupes	198	Lielupes mažieji intakai		Lielupe_Sudupes/198
Lielupe_Sudupes	213	Lielupes mažieji intakai		Lielupe_Sudupes/213
Lielupe_Sudupes	220	Lielupes mažieji intakai		Lielupe_Sudupes/220
Lielupe_Sudupes	Aleja	Lielupes mažieji intakai	Alėja	Lielupe_Sudupes/Aleja
Lielupe_Sudupes	Audruve	Lielupes mažieji intakai	Audruvė	Lielupe_Sudupes/Audruve
Lielupe_Sudupes	Berstalis	Lielupes mažieji	Beržtalys	Lielupe_Sudupes/Berstalis

		intakai		
Lielupe_Sudupes	Kive	Lielupes mažieji intakai	Kivė	Lielupe_Sudupes/Kive
Lielupe_Sudupes	Lepare	Lielupes mažieji intakai	Leparė	Lielupe_Sudupes/Lepare
Lielupe_Sudupes	Oglaine	Lielupes mažieji intakai	Oglainė	Lielupe_Sudupes/Oglaine
Lielupe_Sudupes	Platone	Lielupes mažieji intakai	Platonė	Lielupe_Sudupes/Platone
Lielupe_Sudupes	Plonyte	Lielupes mažieji intakai	Plonyte	Lielupe_Sudupes/Plonyte
Lielupe_Sudupes	Seseve	Lielupes mažieji intakai	Šešėvė	Lielupe_Sudupes/Seseve
Lielupe_Sudupes	Sidarba	Lielupes mažieji intakai	Sidabra	Lielupe_Sudupes/Sidarba
Lielupe_Sudupes	Svete	Lielupes mažieji intakai	Švėtė	Lielupe_Sudupes/Svete
Lielupe_Sudupes	Svetele	Lielupes mažieji intakai	Švėtelė	Lielupe_Sudupes/Svetele
Lielupe_Sudupes	Svirkalnis	Lielupes mažieji intakai	Svirkalnis	Lielupe_Sudupes/Svirkalnis
Lielupe_Sudupes	Svitinys	Lielupes mažieji intakai	Švitinys	Lielupe_Sudupes/Svitinys
Lielupe_Sudupes	Vilikija1	Lielupes mažieji intakai	Vilkija	Lielupe_Sudupes/Vilikija1
Lielupe_Sudupes	Virčiuvis	Lielupes mažieji intakai	Virčiuvis	Lielupe_Sudupes/Virčiuvis
Lielupe_Sudupes	Virsytis	Lielupes mažieji intakai	Viršytis	Lielupe_Sudupes/Virsytis
Lielupe_Sudupes	Ylksys	Lielupes mažieji intakai	Yslykis	Lielupe_Sudupes/Ylksys
Merkys	Merkys	Merkys	Merkys	Merkys/Merkys
Merkys	Pelesa	Merkys	Ūla – Pelesa	Merkys/Pelesa
Merkys	Salcia	Merkys	Šalčia	Merkys/Salcia
Merkys	Varene	Merkys	Varėnė	Merkys/Varene

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Merkys	Verseka	Merkys	Verseka	Merkys/Verseka
Minija	Minija_Kartena	Minija	Minija	Minija/Minija_Kartena
Minija	Minija_zem_kartenas	Minija	Minija	Minija/Minija_zem_kartenas
Minija	Veivirzas	Minija	Veiviržas	Minija/Veivirzas
Minija	Zvelsa	Minija	Žvelsa	Minija/Zvelsa
Musa	Daugyvene	Mūša	Daugyvenė	Musa/Daugyvene
Musa	Kruoja	Mūša	Kruoja	Musa/Kruoja
Musa	Kulpe	Mūša	Kulpė	Musa/Kulpe
Musa	Levuo	Mūša	Lėvuo	Musa/Levuo
Musa	Mazupe	Mūša	Mažupė	Musa/Mazupe
Musa	Musa_kopa	Mūša	Mūša	Musa/Musa_kopa
Musa	Pyvesa	Mūša	Pyvesa	Musa/Pyvesa
Musa	Siladys	Mūša	Šiladis	Musa/Siladys
Musa	Tatula	Mūša	Tatula	Musa/Tatula
Nemunas	Baltoji	Nemunas	Baltoji Ančia	Nemunas/Baltoji
Nemunas	Gege	Nemunas	Gėgė	Nemunas/Gege
Nemunas	Jiesiai	Nemunas	Jiesia	Nemunas/Jiesiai
Nemunas	Miltuva	Nemunas	Miltuva	Nemunas/Miltuva
Nemunas	Nemunas	Nemunas	Nemunas	Nemunas/Nemunas
Nemunas	Perseke	Nemunas	Peršėkė	Nemunas/Perseke
Nemunas	Streva	Nemunas	Strėva	Nemunas/Streva
Nemunas	Streva_ecl_semeliskes	Nemunas	Strėva	Nemunas/Streva_ecl_semeliskes
Nemunas	Sysa_Silute	Nemunas	Šyša	Nemunas/Sysa_Silute
Nemunas	Verkne_Vebyksles	Nemunas	Verknė	Nemunas/Verkne_Vebyksles
Nemunelis	Apasciai	Nemunėlis	Apaščia	Nemunelis/Apasciai
Nemunelis	Nemunelis_LT	Nemunėlis	Nemunėlis	Nemunelis/Nemunelis_LT
Neris	Muse	Neris	Musė	Neris/Muse
Neris	Neris_upe	Neris	Neris	Neris/Neris_upe
Neris	Vilnia	Neris	Vilnia	Neris/Vilnia
Neris	Voke	Neris	Vokė	Neris/Voke
Nevezis	Aluona	Nevėžis	Aluona	Nevezis/Aluona
Nevezis	Barupe	Nevėžis	Barupė	Nevezis/Barupe
Nevezis	Kirstina	Nevėžis	Kiršinas	Nevezis/Kirstina
Nevezis	Nevezis	Nevėžis	Nevėžis	Nevezis/Nevezis
Nevezis	Obelis	Nevėžis	Obelis	Nevezis/Obelis
Nevezis	Panevezis	Nevėžis	Nevėžis	Nevezis/Panevezis
Nevezis	Smilga	Nevėžis	Smilga	Nevezis/Smilga
Nevezis	Susve	Nevėžis	Šušvė	Nevezis/Susve
Nevezis	Upyte	Nevėžis	Upytė	Nevezis/Upyte
Parejais	1127	Pajūrio upės		Parejais/1127
Parejais	1129	Pajūrio upės		Parejais/1129
Parejais	1131	Pajūrio upės		Parejais/1131
Parejais	1158	Pajūrio		Parejais/1158

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		upės		
Parejais	Kretinga	Pajūrio upės	Kretinga	Parejais/Kretinga
Parejais	Kursu_Kapa	Pajūrio upės		Parejais/Kursu_Kapa
Parejais	Kursu_Kapa	Pajūrio upės		Parejais/Kursu_Kapa
Parejais	Kursu_laguna1	Pajūrio upės		Parejais/Kursu_laguna1
Parejais	Kursu_laguna2	Pajūrio upės		Parejais/Kursu_laguna2
Parejais	Kursu_laguna3	Pajūrio upės		Parejais/Kursu_laguna3
Parejais	Kursu_laguna4	Pajūrio upės		Parejais/Kursu_laguna4
Parejais	Kursu_laguna5	Pajūrio upės		Parejais/Kursu_laguna5
Parejais	Osupis1	Pajūrio upės	Ošupis	Parejais/Osupis1
Parejais	Osupis2	Pajūrio upės	Ošupis	Parejais/Osupis2
Parejais	Pareja_Akmene	Pajūrio upės	Akmenė	Parejais/Pareja_Akmene
Parejais	Smeltale	Pajūrio upės	Smeltalė	Parejais/Smeltale
Prieglius	Prieglius	Prieglius	Prieglius	Prieglius/Prieglius
Sesupe	Jotijaa	Šešupė	Jotija	Sesupe/Jotijaa
Sesupe	Nova	Šešupė	Nova	Sesupe/Nova
Sesupe	Pilve	Šešupė	Pilvė	Sesupe/Pilve
Sesupe	Sesupe	Šešupė	Šešupė	Sesupe/Sesupe
Sesupe	Sesupe_upst	Šešupė	Šešupė	Sesupe/Sesupe_upst
Sesupe	Sirvinta	Šešupė	Širvinta	Sesupe/Sirvinta
Sesupe	Viskakis1	Šešupė	Višakis	Sesupe/Viskakis1
Shventoji	Jara	Šventoji	Jara	Shventoji/Jara
Shventoji	Shventoji_A	Šventoji	Šventoji	Shventoji/Shventoji_A
Shventoji	Shventoji_K	Šventoji	Šventoji	Shventoji/Shventoji_K
Shventoji	Sierastis	Šventoji	Siesartis	Shventoji/Sierastis
Shventoji	Sirvinta	Šventoji	Širvinta	Shventoji/Sirvinta
Shventoji	Suraiza	Šventoji	Suraiža-Virinta	Shventoji/Suraiza
Shventoji	Vyžuona	Šventoji	Vyžuona	Shventoji/Vyžuona
Sveentoji	Sventoji	Šventoji	Šventoji	Sveentoji/Sventoji
Sveentoji	Sventoji_Klaip	Šventoji	Šventoji	Sveentoji/Sventoji_Klaip
Venta	222	Venta		Venta/222
Venta	223	Venta		Venta/223
Venta	Dabikina	Venta	Dabikinė	Venta/Dabikina
Venta	Uogys	Venta	Uogys	Venta/Uogys
Venta	Vadakstis	Venta	Vadakstis	Venta/Vadakstis
Venta	Varduva	Venta	Varduva	Venta/Varduva

Venta	Venta	Venta	Venta	Venta/Venta
Venta	Virvyčia	Venta	Virvyčia	Venta/Virvyčia
Zeimena	Dumble1	Žeimena	Dumblė-Kiauna	Zeimena/Dumble1
Zeimena	Kaltena	Žeimena	Žeimena	Zeimena/Kaltena
Zeimena	Lakaja	Žeimena	Lakaja	Zeimena/Lakaja
Zeimena	Stirnele	Žeimena	Stirnelė	Zeimena/Stirnele
Zeimena	Zeimena	Žeimena	Žeimena	Zeimena/Zeimena

The initial model parameter values in all watersheds were set equivalent to the model parameters of Šušvė. Further, we selected 15 watersheds with sufficient information for the calibration of the SWAT model. The requirements for selection of these basins were (1) availability of at least 7 years of daily flow and monthly water quality measurements, (2) location of the watershed at the upstream part of the river basin. The selected watersheds are shown on Fig.36.

Fig. 36. Watersheds selected for calibration.

In the present report we include the calibration and validation results for these watersheds summarised in Table 18. Quantitative watershed parameters are given in Table 10. The size of watersheds vary from 100 to 2000 square kilometres. The watershed delineation (with hydrometric, water quality and meteorological observations stations) for these watersheds (except Šušvė shown in previous sections) are shown in Figs 37-50.

Table. 18. Quantitative parameters of considered model setups.

Basin	River	Setup name	Area	Subbasins	HRU
Jura	Šešupe	Sesupe_Skirgalai	1898	32	2025
Nemunas	Šyša	Sysa_Silute	375	5	401
Dubysa	Dubysa	Dubysa	1969	31	2275
Jura	Jūra	Jura_Taurage	1689	22	1491
Musa	Tatula	Tatula	451	7	557
Bartuva	Bartuva	Bartuva_Skuodas	611	10	608
Dauguva	Birveta	Bivyte	548	8	456
Lielupe	Platonis	Platone	131	2	93
Lielupe	Ylksys	Ylksys	100	2	72
Minija	Veivirzas	Veivirzas	677	12	579
Musa	Daugyvene	Daugyvene	494	7	415
Nemunas	Miltuva	Miltuva	783	14	708
Nevezis	Šušve	Susve	1180	13	1054
Shventoji	Širvinta	Sirvinta	917	10	582
Minija	Minija	Minija_Kartena	1228	17	1279

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Fig 37. The subbasin delineation, river network, meteorological, hydrometric and water quality stations for Bartuva watershed.

Fig. 38 The subbasin delineation, river network, meteorological, hydrometric and water quality stations for Šyša-Šilutė watershed (Nemunas basin).

Fig. 39. The subbasin delineation, river network, meteorological, hydrometric and water quality stations for Dubysa watershed.

Fig. 40. The subbasin delineation, river network, meteorological, hydrometric and water quality stations for Jūra-Tauragės watershed.

Fig. 41. The subbasin delineation, river network, meteorological, hydrometric and water quality stations for Tatula watershed (Mūša basin).

Fig. 42. The subbasin delineation, river network, meteorological, hydrometric and water quality stations for Bārtuva-Škuodas watershed.

Fig. 43. The subbasin delineation, river network, meteorological, hydrometric and water quality stations for Birveta watershed (Dauguva basin).

Fig. 44. The subbasin delineation, river network, meteorological, hydrometric and water quality stations for Platonis watershed (Lielupe basin).

Fig. 45. The subbasin delineation, river network, meteorological, hydrometric and water quality stations for Yksis watershed (Lielupe basin).

Fig. 46. The subbasin delineation, river network, meteorological, hydrometric and water quality stations for Veivirzas watershed (Minija basin).

Fig. 47. The subbasin delineation, river network, meteorological, hydrometric and water quality stations for Daugyvene watershed (Mūša basin).

Fig. 48. The subbasin delineation, river network, meteorological, hydrometric and water quality stations for Miltuva watershed (Nemunas basin).

Fig. 49. The subbasin delineation, river network, meteorological, hydrometric and water quality stations for Širvinta watershed (Šventoji basin).

Fig. 50. The subbasin delineation, river network, meteorological, hydrometric and water quality stations for Minija-Kartena watershed.

The calibration of the hydrology and water quality for the 15 watersheds was performed with initial use of default (Šušve) “Lithuanian” model parameters. The modified parameter values are included in the electronic deliverables.

The summary of the calibration and validation results are given in Table 19, while the time graphs of the observed and calculated daily and monthly discharges, monthly loads of N-NO₃, N-NH₄, N-org, P-PO₄, P-Org, suspended sediments, BOD₇ and dissolved oxygen are presented in Figs. 51 – 175. The time graphs contain all calculation period, whilst the calibration and validation periods are separated in Table 19 and color –coded according to Moriasi et al (2007).

We conclude that the approach of detailed calibration of pilot (Šušve) watershed has yielded a result of relatively easier calibration of other watersheds. The values of the calibration parameters (if given in % then relative to Šušve watershed) which are different from the Šušve “default” values are summarised in Table 20. No parameter modifications were needed for Minija watershed.

The results of calibration are similar for all considered rivers. Both calibration and validation results for monthly discharges may be estimated as good to very good according to NSE value and very good for PBIAS value.

The calibration according to PBIAS is very good for almost all water quality parameters. Meanwhile monthly NSE values are unsatisfactory for all loads except N-NO₃.

The validation was not possible for some watersheds due to insufficient long data series of data. The exceptions are: (1) Q validation was not possible for Tatula, Birtveta, Platonis, Daugyvene, Šyša, Šešupe, (2) both WQ calibration and validation was possible only for Bärtuva, Birtveta, Veivirzas, Šušve, (3) only hydrological calibration/validation was possible

for Miltuva and Ylksys.

Table 19. Calibration and validation results for 15 watersheds.

Watershed	Jura-Šešupe-Skirgalai	Nemunas-Šyša-Šilute	Dubysa-Dubysa
Q_station	Šešupe-Skirgalais	Šyša-Šilute	Dubysa-Lyduvenai
WQ_Station	Šešupe-ties-Skirgalai	Šyša_žemiau_Šilute	Dubysa_aukščiau_Seredžiaus
Q_kalibr	2006-2010	2006-2010	2000-2005
WQ_kalibr	2000-2005	2005-2010	2005-2010
Q NSE daily	0,72	0,5	0,65
Q NSE monthly	0,85	0,67	0,74
Qbias	6,70%	2,60%	-7,80%
NO3 NSE	0,43	-18,67	0,47
N-NO3	10,20%	10,40%	3,90%
N-NH4	8,90%	-1,40%	16,00%
N-Org	3,30%	5,20%	-6,90%
P-PO4	16,10%	-17,00%	-9,10%
P-Org	-1,30%	15,60%	-35,60%
SS	8,30%	10,00%	27,80%
BOD7	4,10%	-30,40%	23,10%
DOX	1,70%	13,30%	-15,70%
Q_valid			2006-2010
WQ_Valid			
Q NSE daily			0,61
Q NSE monthly			0,72
Qbias			0,70%
NO3 NSE			
N-NO3			
N-NH4			
N-Org			
P-PO4			
P-Org			
SS			
BOD7			
DOX			

Table 19 (continued). Calibration and validation results for 15 watersheds.

Watershed	Jūra-Taurage	Mūša-Tatula	Bartuva-Skuodas
Q_station	Jūra_Taurage	Tatula_Trečionys	Bartuva_Skoudas
WQ_Station	Jūra_aukščiau_Taurage	Tatula_ties_Trečionimis	Bartuva_žemiau Skoudas
Q_kalibr	2000-2005	2006-2010	2000-2005
WQ_kalibr	2000-2004	2000-2004	2000-2005
Q NSE daily	0,65	0,65	0,67
Q NSE monthly	0,79	0,82	0,82
Qbias	-0,50%	-7,60%	-5,60%
NO3 NSE	0,46	0,16	0,45
N-NO3	2,40%	10,90%	-4,50%
N-NH4	0,20%	-8,20%	-10,90%
N-Org	-1,10%	23,80%	26,70%
P-PO4	15,20%	-2,40%	-1,30%
P-Org	2,70%	13,00%	5,80%
SS	3,30%	37,50%	33,00%
BOD7	13,30%	11,10%	26,80%
DOX	7,60%	5,20%	1,10%
Q_valid	2006-2010		2006-2010
WQ_Valid			2006-2010
Q NSE daily	0,71		0,7
Q NSE monthly	0,85		0,86
Qbias	-11,10%		-2,70%
NO3 NSE			0,82
N-NO3			23,40%
N-NH4			8,50%
N-Org			-22,70%
P-PO4			-24,60%
P-Org			12,50%
SS			-22,40%
BOD7			-37,40%
DOX			13,30%

 very good satisfactory

 good unsatisfactory

Table 19 (continued). Calibration and validation results for 15 watersheds.

Watershed	Dauguva-Bivyte	Lielupe-Platone	Lielupe-Ylksys
Q_station	Svyła_Gunatuninkai	Platonis_Vainekiai	Ylksys_Kyburiai
WQ_Station	Birveta_Baltarusijos pasienyje	Platonis_paienyje	
Q_kalibr	2008-2010	2008-2010	2000-2005
WQ_kalibr	2000-2005	2005-2010	
Q NSE daily	0,56	0,73	0,76
Q NSE monthly	0,87	0,87	0,84
Qbias	-6,70%	0,90%	1,80%
NO3 NSE	0,38	0,6	
N-NO3	8,80%	-9,60%	
N-NH4	-2,40%	2,40%	
N-Org	25,50%	-16,70%	
P-PO4	20,80%	-23,20%	
P-Org	35,60%	18,50%	
SS	36,60%	34,40%	
BOD7	35,00%	-27,90%	
DOX	18,20%	39,80%	
Q_valid			2006-2010
WQ_Valid	2006-2010		
Q NSE daily			0,51
Q NSE monthly			0,61
Qbias			1,70%
NO3 NSE	0,46		
N-NO3	6,70%		
N-NH4	-31,80%		
N-Org	-30,30%		
P-PO4	-19,00%		
P-Org	-20,60%		
SS	-37,40%		
BOD7	-63,00%		
DOX	-10,40%		

 very good
 satisfactory
 good
 unsatisfactory

Table 19 (continued). Calibration and validation results for 15 watersheds.

Watershed	Minija-Veivirzas	Mūša-Daugyvene	Nemunas-Miltuva
Q_station	Upita_Eidukai	Daugyvene_Rimšoniai	Miltuva_Žindaiciai
WQ_Station	Veivirzas_Veivirzas	Daugyvene_žiotyse	
Q_kalibr	2000-2006	2006-2010	2000-2006
WQ_kalibr	2001-2006	2008-2010	
Q NSE daily	0,44	0,56	0,62
Q NSE monthly	0,67	0,7	0,72
Qbias	7,50%	-7,00%	12,60%
NO3 NSE	0,14	0,66	
N-NO3	8,40%	-10,60%	
N-NH4	-39,00%	10,60%	
N-Org	-26,80%	-0,20%	
P-PO4	-38,80%	20,20%	
P-Org	1,90%	6,10%	
SS	38,50%	12,90%	
BOD7	-5,00%	-0,40%	
DOX	-4,30%	11,50%	
Q_valid	2008-2010		2007-2010
WQ_Valid			
Q NSE daily	0,47		0,65
Q NSE monthly	0,79		0,81
Qbias	1,50%		-13,10%
NO3 NSE	0,72		
N-NO3	20,50%		
N-NH4	-14,00%		
N-Org	-6,70%		
P-PO4	39,60%		
P-Org	18,00%		
SS	-39,10%		
BOD7	-8,80%		
DOX	-1,60%		

 very good
 satisfactory
 good
 unsatisfactory

Table 19 (continued). Calibration and validation results for 15 watersheds.

Watershed	Nevežis-Šušve	Šventoji-Širvinta	Minija-Kartena
Q_station	Šušve_Jošvainai	Širvinta_Liukonys	Minija_Kartena
WQ_Station	Šušve_Žiotyse	Širvinta_žemiau Širvintu	Minija_aukščiau_Plunges
Q_kalibr	2003-2007	2000-2005	2000-2005
WQ_kalibr	2000-2005	2000-2005	2000-2005
Q NSE daily	0,58	0,56	0,58
Q NSE monthly	0,72	0,61	0,73
Qbias	-9,40%	6,10%	-9,30%
NO3 NSE	0,6	0,45	-0,09
N-NO3	-16,00%	14,00%	10,50%
N-NH4	6,80%	-10,30%	9,50%
N-Org	-3,40%	7,90%	-8,70%
P-PO4	-23,20%	4,10%	37,30%
P-Org	33,30%	13,20%	38,60%
SS	-0,20%	13,90%	39,20%
BOD7	7,30%	-8,70%	-33,10%
DOX	-4,80%	2,50%	10,00%
Q_valid	2008-2010	2006-2010	2006-2010
WQ_Valid	2006-2010		
Q NSE daily	0,73	0,7	0,62
Q NSE monthly	0,87	0,84	0,77
Qbias	9,80%	-8,70%	7,80%
NO3 NSE	0,53		
N-NO3	17,20%		
N-NH4	-9,80%		
N-Org	-22,20%		
P-PO4	17,60%		
P-Org	-3,10%		
SS	-14,40%		
BOD7	-33,30%		
DOX	26,20%		

 very good
 good

 satisfactory
 unsatisfactory

Fig. 51. Jūra – Šešupe - Skirgailai. Daily discharge. Green – model, red – observations.

Fig. 52. Jūra – Šešupe - Skirgailai. Monthly discharge. Green – model, red – observations

Fig. 53. Jūra – Šešupe - Skirgailai. Monthly NO₃ load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 54. Jūra – Šešupe - Skirgailai. Monthly NH₄ load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 55. Jūra – Šešupe - Skirgailai. Monthly N-Org load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 56. Jūra – Šešupe - Skirgailai. Monthly P-PO4 load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 57. Jūra – Šešupe - Skirgailai. Monthly P-Org load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 58. Jūra – Šešupe - Skirgailai. Monthly suspended sediment load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 59. Jūra – Šešupe - Skirgailai. Monthly BOD7 load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 60. Jūra – Šešupe - Skirgailai. Monthly DO load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 61 Nemunas – Šyša - Šilute. Daily discharge. Green – model, red – observations.

Fig. 62. Nemunas – Šyša - Šilute. Monthly discharge. Green – model, red – observations

Fig. 63. Nemunas – Šyša - Šilute. Monthly NO₃ load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 64. Nemunas – Šyša - Šilute. Monthly NH₄ load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 65. Nemunas – Šyša - Šilute. Monthly N-Org load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 66. Nemunas – Šyša - Šilute. Monthly P-PO4 load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 67. Nemunas – Šyša - Šilute. Monthly P-Org load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 68. Nemunas – Šyša - Šilute. Monthly suspended sediment load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 69. Nemunas – Šyša - Šilute. Monthly BOD7 load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 70. Nemunas – Šyša - Šilute. Monthly DO load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 71. Dubysa - Dubysa. Daily discharge. Green – model, red – observations.

Fig. 72. Dubysa - Dubysa. Monthly discharge. Green – model, red – observations

Fig. 73. Dubysa - Dubysa. Monthly NO₃ load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 74. Dubysa - Dubysa. Monthly NH₄ load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 75. Dubysa - Dubysa. Monthly N-Organic load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 76. Dubysa - Dubysa. Monthly P-PO4 load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 77. Dubysa - Dubysa. Monthly P-Org load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 78. Dubysa - Dubysa. Monthly suspended sediment load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 79. Dubysa - Dubysa. Monthly BOD7 load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 80. Dubysa - Dubysa. Monthly DO load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 81. Jūra – Taurage. Daily discharge. Green – model, red – observations.

Fig. 82. Jūra – Taurage. Monthly discharge. Green – model, red – observations

Fig. 83. Jūra – Taurage. Monthly NO₃ load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 84. Jūra – Taurage. Monthly NH₄ load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 85. Jūra – Taurage. Monthly N-Org load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 86. Jūra – Taurage. Monthly P-PO4 load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 87. Jūra – Taurage. Monthly P-Org load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 88. Jūra – Taurage. Monthly suspended sediment load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 89. Jūra – Taurage. Monthly BOD7 load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 90. Jūra – Taurage. Monthly DO load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 91. Mūša - Tatula. Daily discharge. Green – model, red – observations.

Fig. 92. Mūša - Tatula. Monthly discharge. Green – model, red – observations

Fig. 93. Mūša - Tatula. Monthly NO₃ load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 94. Mūša - Tatula. Monthly NH₄ load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 95. Mūša - Tatula. Monthly N-Org load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 96. Mūša - Tatula. Monthly P-PO4 load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 97. Mūša - Tatula. Monthly P-Org load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 98. Mūša - Tatula. Monthly suspended sediment load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 99. Mūša - Tatula. Monthly BOD7 load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 100. Mūša - Tatula. Monthly DO load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 101. Bartuva - Skuodas. Daily discharge. Green – model, red – observations.

Fig. 102. Bartuva – Skuodas. Monthly discharge. Green – model, red – observations

Fig. 103. Bartuva - Skuodas. Monthly NO₃ load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 104. Bartuva - Skuodas. Monthly NH₄ load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 105. Bartuva - Skuodas. Monthly N-Org load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 106. Bartuva - Skuodas. Monthly P-PO4 load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 107. Bartuva - Skuodas. Monthly P-Org load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 108. Bartuva - Skuodas. Monthly suspended sediment load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 109. Bartuva - Skuodas. Monthly BOD7 load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 110. Bartuva - Skuodas. Monthly DO load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 111. Dauguva - Birveta. Daily discharge. Green – model, red – observations.

Fig. 112. Dauguva - Birveta. Monthly discharge. Green – model, red – observations

Fig. 113. Dauguva - Birveta. Monthly NO₃ load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 114. Dauguva - Birveta. Monthly NH₄ load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 115. Dauguva - Birveta. Monthly N-Org load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 116. Dauguva - Birveta. Monthly P-PO4 load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 117. Dauguva - Birveta. Monthly P-Org load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 118. Dauguva - Birveta. Monthly suspended sediment load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 119. Dauguva - Birveta. Monthly BOD7 load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 120. Dauguva - Birveta. Monthly DO load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 121. Lielupe - Platone. Daily discharge. Green – model, red – observations.

Fig. 122. Lielupe - Platone. Monthly discharge. Green – model, red – observations

Fig. 123. Lielupe - Platone. Monthly NO₃ load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 124. Lielupe - Platone. Monthly NH₄ load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 125. Lielupe - Platone. Monthly N-Org load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 126. Lielupe - Platone. Monthly P-PO4 load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 127. Lielupe - Platone. Monthly P-Org load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 128. Lielupe - Platone. Monthly suspended sediment load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 129. Lielupe - Platone. Monthly BOD7 load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 130. Lielupe - Platone. Monthly DO load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 131. Lielupe - Yksys. Daily discharge. Green – model, red – observations.

Fig. 132. Lielupe - Yksys. Monthly discharge. Green – model, red – observations

Fig. 133. Minija - Veivirzas. Daily discharge. Green – model, red – observations.

Fig. 134. Minija - Veivirzas. Monthly discharge. Green – model, red – observations

Fig. 135. Minija - Veivirzas. Monthly NO₃ load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 136. Minija - Veivirzas. Monthly NH₄ load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 137. Minija - Veivirzas. Monthly N-Org load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 138. Minija - Veivirzas. Monthly P-PO4 load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 139. Minija - Veivirzas. Monthly P-Org load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 140. Minija - Veivirzas. Monthly suspended sediment load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 141. Minija - Veivizas. Monthly BOD7 load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 142. Minija - Veivizas. Monthly DO load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 143. Mūša - Daugyvene. Daily discharge. Green – model, red – observations.

Fig. 144. Mūša - Daugyvene. Monthly discharge. Green – model, red – observations

Fig. 145. Mūša - Daugyvene. Monthly NO₃ load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 146. Mūša - Daugyvene. Monthly NH₄ load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 147. Mūša - Daugyvene. Monthly N-Org load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 148. Mūša - Daugyvene. Monthly P-PO4 load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 149. Mūša - Daugyvene. Monthly P-Org load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 150. Mūša - Daugyvene. Monthly suspended sediment load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 151. Mūša - Daugyvene. Monthly BOD7 load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 152. Mūša - Daugyvene. Monthly DO load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 153. Nemunas - Miltuva. Daily discharge. Green – model, red – observations.

Fig. 154. Nemunas - Miltuva. Monthly discharge. Green – model, red – observations

Fig. 155. Šventoji - Širvinta. Daily discharge. Green – model, red – observations.

Fig. 156. Šventoji - Širvinta. Monthly discharge. Green – model, red – observations

Fig. 157. Šventoji - Širvinta. Monthly NO₃ load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 158. Šventoji - Širvinta. Monthly NH₄ load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 159. Šventoji - Širvinta. Monthly N-Org load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 160. Šventoji - Širvinta. Monthly P-PO4 load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 161. Šventoji - Širvinta. Monthly P-Org load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 162. Šventoji - Širvinta. Monthly suspended sediment load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 163. Šventoji - Širvinta. Monthly BOD7 load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 164. Šventoji - Širvinta. Monthly DO load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 165. Minija - Kartena. Daily discharge. Green – model, red – observations.

Fig. 166. Minija - Kartena. Monthly discharge. Green – model, red – observations

Fig. 167. Minija - Kartena. Monthly NO₃ load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 168. Minija - Kartena. Monthly NH₄ load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 169. Minija - Kartena. Monthly N-Org load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 170. Minija - Kartena. Monthly P-PO4 load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 171. Minija - Kartena. Monthly P-Org load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 172. Minija - Kartena. Monthly suspended sediment load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 173. Minija - Kartena. Monthly BOD7 load, green – model, red dots – observations

Fig. 175. Minija - Kartena. Monthly DO load, green – model, red dots – observations

Table 15. The values of the calibration parameters which differ from the default (Šušve) for 15 watersheds.

	Sesupe_Skirgalai	Sysa_Silute	Dubysa_Dubysa	Jura_Taurage
HRU.CANMX	15	20		
SOL.SOL_AWC	10%	91%		-10%
SOL.USLE_K				
SOL.SOL_K				
MGT.CN2	-0,25%	20%		
MGT.USLE_P	0,5	0,1		
SWQ.RS1		1		
SWQ.RS2				
SWQ.RS3				
SWQ.RS4	0,36	1,25		0,33
SWQ.RS5	0,36	2		0,3
SWQ.RK1				0,15
SWQ.RK2	0,5	0,5		
SWQ.RK3	0,25			
SWQ.BC1	1	3		1,5
SWQ.BC2		4		
SWQ.BC3	0,09	0,4	0,04	
SWQ.BC4	0,18	0,4		0,1
BSN.SPCON	0,0004	2,00E-04	1,00E-04	
BSN.CDN	0,25	1	0,04	0,2
BSN.SPEXP		2		
BSN.NPERCO				
BSN.SURLAG				
GW.HLIFE_NGW		10		150
GW.ALPHA_BF		0,05		
GW.RCHRG_DP				

Table 15 (continued). The values of the calibration parameters which differ from the default (Šušve) for 15 watersheds.

	Tatula	Bartuva_Skoudas	Dauguva_Bivyte	Platone	Ylksys
HRU.CANMX		5			
SOL.SOL_AWC	-23%	-27%	-30%		11%
SOL.USLE_K			-92%		
SOL.SOL_K				-23%	
MGT.CN2	-11%	-10%		-0,45%	
MGT.USLE_P	0,2	0,3	0,5	0,1	
SWQ.RS1	0,5	0,6		5	
SWQ.RS2					
SWQ.RS3					
SWQ.RS4	0,2	0,25	0,2	0,5	
SWQ.RS5	1	0,4		11	
SWQ.RK1		0,01	0,01		
SWQ.RK2	0,5			1,5	
SWQ.RK3	0,2	0,15	0,01	0,12	
SWQ.BC1	1	0,5	3	40	
SWQ.BC2				40	
SWQ.BC3	0,2	0,15	0,15	0,3	
SWQ.BC4	1,1	0,38	0,6	0,24	
BSN.SPCON	1,00E-04	2,00E-05	0,00004	0,00001	
BSN.CDN		0,4	0,25		
BSN.SPEXP	2,5	2		3	
BSN.NPERCO	1				
BSN.SURLAG					
GW.HLIFE_NGW		365		3000	
GW.ALPHA_BF		0,08			0,1
GW.RCHRG_DP	-0,05	0,01			

Table 15 (continued). The values of the calibration parameters which differ from the default (Šušve) for 15 watersheds.

	Veivirzas	Daugyvene	Miltuva	Susve	Shventojis_Sirvinta
HRU.CANMX	15			15	20
SOL.SOL_AWC	20%	-10%		-2,6%	21%
SOL.USLE_K					
SOL.SOL_K					
MGT.CN2	-12%			-5%	-17%
MGT.USLE_P	0,5	0,3			0,5
SWQ.RS1	0,2				0,05
SWQ.RS2					0,01
SWQ.RS3					0,3
SWQ.RS4	0,001	0,07			0,04
SWQ.RS5	0,05	1		0,6	0,07
SWQ.RK1	0,03				0,25
SWQ.RK2	2,5				0,5
SWQ.RK3	0,03	0,25			0,03
SWQ.BC1	0,1			3	0,05
SWQ.BC2					
SWQ.BC3	0,45	0,12		0,09	0,08
SWQ.BC4	1,9	0,2		0,24	0,95
BSN.SPCON	0,0001	0,0001			0,0001
BSN.CDN	0,5			0,04	0,25
BSN.SPEXP	2	2			2
BSN.NPERCO					
BSN.SURLAG	0,5				
GW.HLIFE_NGW	365				
GW.ALPHA_BF	0,2	0,06	0,12		0,04
GW.RCHRG_DP		0,01		0,09	

3. Concluding remarks and compliance with the Working Plan

Recommendations for data gathering and data processing improvements

The system of the data gathering and processing can be assessed by the contents of the databases supplied by AAA. Therefore our possibilities in recommending improvements are limited to the contents of these databases:

1. The frequency of discharge (waterlevel) observations and water quality sampling in rivers is consistent (once per day / once per month) and need no improvements.
2. Several water quality stations are closed in 2005. We consider this as major downgrade of the observation data series. A general recommendation might be in avoiding changes as much as possible in the list of observed parameters, sampling location and frequency for all stations where data time series are historically available.
3. We recommend to establish monitoring stations on the border – crossing for transboundary rivers (both in-and outflowing) if the catchment area at the border-crossing point exceeds certain value.
4. We recommend to perform additional water quality monitoring campaigns (1) for coverage of unmonitored rivers, (2) to measure water quality parameters upstream and downstream reservoirs. Such non-regular data “points” may improve the situation in combination with the assessment of the model results.
5. We recommend to gather monthly data on water pollution point sources and equalise the set of measured water quality parameters in effluent.

Recommendations for the future development of prepared modelling system

The further development of prepared modelling system is foreseen already in this project; it includes calculation of the N-P loads, development of GIS based decision support system, scenario calculation and linking with MIKE11 and MIKE21 model setups. Besides these developments and application we may recommend consideration of:

1. Alternative calibration of SWAT setup for only N and P load calculation (without usage of Qual module for stream processes) might be recommended due the linkage of SWAT with Qual module seems to undergo serious improvements in SWAT community.
2. The routine use and update of the modelling system with actual input data should be performed. We recommend to do this on annual basis.
3. The reconsideration and recalibration of the modelling system is essentially required at regular time intervals (5 to 6 years) in association with (1) improvements in the process description in SWAT models, (2) changes in the land use and management praxis.
4. We recommend continuous work to increase the spatial resolution of the modelling system after this project (i.e. building of SWAT “watersheds” instead of current “subbasins”). This process has to be performed evolutionary (watershed by watershed).

watershed) and model calibration procedure has to be used for the critical review of the model input data. The procedures have to be developed for the input data correction (and/or detalisation) if the model calculations indicate the input data quality problems.

5. The systematic review of input data issues may be performed for the locations where the observations indicate outlying values from the modelling results and/or sudden changes in the time series.

Compliance with working plan

By now the Project WG has in general respected the Working plan proposed in the Technical proposal. Within the Project IG it was internally agreed that the 1st Draft Interim report will be submitted by October 31, 2011. This does not influence the overall project progress due to the technical specification of the tender documentation required the fulfilment of 1st stage within 5 months.

The table below shows the actual status of the project implementation in 20 weeks.

Table 21. The actual status of the project implementation in 20 weeks.

Week	Activities	Milestones	Deliverables	Reports	Comments on status
1 ¹	A1, A2, A15, A17				Implemented The water quality modelling system (WQMS) developed within A5 will be integrated with MIKE 11 model (A15) and MIKE 21 (A17)
2	A1, A2, A15, A17				
3	A1, A2				Implemented
4	A1, A2	M1			Modelling system selected an approved
5	A2, A3				Implemented
6	A2, A3				
7	A2, A3				
8	A2, A4	M2			Model performance and calibration results approved
9	A2, A4, A5				Implemented
10	A2, A5				Implemented
11	A2, A5				
12	A2, A5				
13	A5				
14	A5				Implemented
15	A5				
16	A5				
17	A5				
18	A5	M3	D1		
19	A6, A7				

¹ The official project start date is May 31, 2011.

The 1st Interim Report of Project “Development of methodics and modelling system of nitrogen and phosphorus load calculation for surface waters of Lithuania”

20 ²	A6, A7	M4, M5		I1D	Training accomplished Task 1 accomplished
21					
22					The Draft of the first Interim report is submitted by October 31, 2011

Milestones:

- M1: Modelling system selected and approved;
- M2: Model performance and calibration results approved;
- M3: Water quality model for Lithuania developed and calibrated;
- M4: Training accomplished;
- M5: Task 1 accomplished

Deliverables:

- D1: Water quality model for Lithuania;

Reports:

- I1D: Draft of the 1st interim report (result of activity A7);

²Week 20 ends on October 18, 2011

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